

Association between intelectin-1, sleep quality, and insulin resistance in infertile women of reproductive age

Jehan A. Mohammad¹

¹ Department of Pharmacognosy and Medicinal Plants, College of Pharmacy, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

² Department of Clinical Laboratory Sciences, College of Pharmacy, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

³ Department of Chemistry, College of Sciences, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

Corresponding author: Marwah H. Mohammed (marwaalmola@uomosul.edu.iq)

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Abstract

Intelectin-1, in addition to its anti-inflammatory activity, may play a role in the pathogenesis of type II diabetes and sleep disorders. However, its exact role in humans still requires further investigation. This study was conducted on 175 women, divided into two groups: 90 patients with infertility (cases) and 85 fertile women (controls). In addition to sociodemographic and anthropometric measurements, the study collected information on intelectin-1, the Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI), fasting blood sugar, insulin level, insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), the quantitative insulin sensitivity check index (QUICKI), the homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function (HOMA- β), insulin sensitivity, and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH). Intelectin-1 was shown to be a reliable biomarker for the assessment of menstrual irregularity and sleep quality. Moreover, intelectin-1 showed a significant negative correlation with body mass index, menstrual regularity, PSQI, and fasting blood sugar regulation, while it had a significant positive correlation with HOMA- β and AMH.

Keywords

biomarker, infertility, omentin, prediction

Introduction

Adipose tissue secretes peptides and proteins called adipokines, also referred to as adipocytokines (Pogodziński et al. 2022). Omentin is one of these adipokines that has gained interest recently, since it was shown to be largely synthesized in visceral fat, while the subcutaneous adipose tissue expresses a minor quantity of it (Hussein et al. 2024). Intelectin-1 (ITLN-1), another name for omentin-1, is the most common type of serum omentin in humans (Gao et al. 2025). Omentin-1 has anti-inflammatory activity. Recent studies have shown that it may inhibit the production of vascular

cell adhesion molecule (VCAM-1) in smooth muscle cells and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) in vascular endothelial cells, respectively, stimulated by TNF- α (Gao et al. 2025).

Increased visceral fat in the abdomen is linked to coronary heart disease, type 2 diabetes, and insulin resistance (Zheng et al. 2023). A state of hyperinsulinemia brought on by a number of factors is known as insulin resistance (IR), in which the body's capacity to absorb and use glucose is reduced, leading to an increase in the compensatory release of insulin to keep blood glucose levels steady (Lee et al. 2022). Adults with sleep disturbances are more likely to have insulin resistance, glucose intolerance, and

type 2 diabetes. Numerous metabolic diseases that significantly increase morbidity and mortality have been linked to sleep disruption (Reutrakul et al. 2022).

Infertility is a condition that can seriously jeopardize a patient's social and physical well-being. The most prevalent risk factors for infertility in women are polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), diabetes, and thyroid disorders. Fertility can also be impacted by lifestyle choices, including sleep, diet, smoking, and alcohol consumption (Li et al. 2024). Sleep disruption is a prevalent public health concern that has a detrimental impact on physical and emotional well-being and lowers quality of life. The human body's numerous physiological systems depend on sleep (Carpi et al. 2024). Lack of sleep is linked to chronic illnesses and conditions, including diabetes, obesity, and thyroid disorders, some of which may be risk factors for female infertility. Throughout a woman's life cycle, from menstruation to pregnancy to menopause, her risk of developing sleep problems varies continuously. According to recent studies, there is a significant correlation between female infertility and sleep disruptions, indicating that sleep may be important for reproductive health (Li et al. 2024). Women's mental and physical well-being, hormone balance, and even pregnancy outcomes are all specifically affected by these conditions (Khan et al. 2023). It is important to remember that both sleep restriction and sleep deprivation are stressful situations that raise cortisol release, which might account for the impairment of insulin function and glucose absorption (Azuara-Alvarez et al. 2023). Finally, it has been proposed that the anti-inflammatory activities of ITLN-1 are well established. It is well known that inflammation can interfere with sleep. Consequently, ITLN-1's anti-inflammatory properties may improve the quality of sleep by reducing inflammation-related sleep disruptions (Wahba et al. 2021).

This study aimed to evaluate serum intelectin-1 levels in a group of infertile women and compare them with a healthy group. It also investigates potential correlations between intelectin-1, insulin resistance, and sleep quality as new markers for infertility and assesses whether these levels can serve as an innovative biomarker in infertility. The study emphasizes the significance of these findings in improving clinical treatment and management of the condition.

Materials and methods

Patients

This study was a case-control study conducted at Al Salam Teaching Hospital in Mosul City (north of Iraq). In addition, patient samples were obtained from private clinics run by Dr. Asmaa Alsenjary, who specializes in gynecology and obstetrics (assisted reproductive techniques). Ethical approval was obtained from the Collegiate Committee for Medical Research Ethics (code: CCMRE-phA-24-11). The study began in January 2025 and ended in June 2025. A total of 175 ladies were included and divided into two groups. The case group consisted of 90 ladies with infertility, matched

with 85 fertile ladies who had at least one childbirth. The study participants were between 20 and 43 years of age.

All members of the case group were married women who lived with their husbands and had not used any method of contraception for at least 1 year but had no children. Women with endometriosis, uterine fibroids, breast cancer, epilepsy, or migraine, as well as those with hormone-dependent malignancies or metabolic disorders, were excluded from the study. Furthermore, patients with hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism, diabetes, mental illness, serious heart, liver, or kidney dysfunction, and those receiving estrogen replacement treatment were also excluded. The control group had not taken oral contraceptives in the previous 3 months and showed no clinical evidence of hyperandrogenemia or polycystic ovarian symptoms.

Data collection

Every participant and their accompanying individuals were provided with a customized explanation of the study's objective, along with responses to any inquiries they raised. The research included individuals who met the inclusion criteria and provided written informed consent. The study did not include patients who refused to provide informed consent. After obtaining consent, 90 ladies with infertility and 85 fertile ladies with at least one childbirth who met the inclusion criteria were recruited for the investigation. Data were obtained directly through interviews with all participants in this study, during which the researcher personally administered a prepared questionnaire. Study participants were informed that the data would be kept confidential and that no one other than the researcher would have access to it.

Anthropometric measurements

The participants' body weights were measured using a German weight scale (Beurer) while wearing thin clothing, without shoes, and on an empty stomach. To determine the participants' heights, they were asked to stand upright with their heads horizontal, legs together, and heels, buttocks, and back against the wall. The body mass index (BMI) was calculated by dividing weight (in kilograms) by squared height (in meters) (Mohajan et al. 2023).

Intelectin-1 and biochemical parameters assay

All blood samples were collected between 09:00 and 09:30 a.m. after a 6–8-hour fast and 30 minutes of resting in the sitting position. Blood was collected during the second or third day of the menstrual cycle using disposable plastic syringes and needles. Venous fasting blood samples (10 mL) were obtained by venipuncture from patients and healthy volunteers, transferred to a plain tube (without anticoagulant), and allowed to clot for 30 minutes at room temperature. The serum was extracted by centrifuging the clotted blood at 402×g for 10 minutes. Serum samples were used for variable detection and stored at –20 °C until analysis.

An additional 5 mL blood sample was collected for serum intelectin-1 level testing. Using an ELISA microplate reader (BioTek, USA), the Human Intelectin-1 ELISA Kit (E0155Hu, Bioassay Technology Laboratory, Shanghai, China) was used to determine intelectin-1 levels based on the sandwich principle. The results were expressed in nanograms per milliliter. Serum glucose was estimated using a kit (KA0831, Abnova, Taipei, Taiwan); AMH was determined by a kit (E-EL-H0317, Elabscience, Houston, TX, USA); and insulin by a kit (KA0921, Abnova). Insulin resistance (IR) was determined by the homeostasis model assessment [HOMA-IR = fasting blood insulin ($\mu\text{IU/mL}$) \times fasting blood glucose (mg/dL) / 405] (Dae-Jeong Koo et al. 2021). The quantitative insulin sensitivity check index was calculated as [QUICKI = $1 - \{(\log \text{insulin, } \mu\text{IU/mL}) + (\log \text{glucose, mg/dL})\}$] (Khan et al. 2024). Insulin sensitivity (IS) was expressed as $IS = 1/IR$ (Koo et al. 2021). Homeostatic model assessment of β -cell function (HOMA- $\beta\%$) was calculated as $\text{HOMA-}\beta\% = (360 \times \text{fasting insulin } (\mu\text{IU/mL})) / (\text{fasting glucose (mg/dL)} - 63)$ (Tepper et al. 2016).

The Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI)

The Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI), established in 1989 (Buysse et al. 1989), helps assess the quality of individuals' sleep. It consists of 19 self-reported items and 6 items rated by roommates or bed partners; only the self-reported items are used to calculate the final score. The self-rated items form seven components: subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, sleep drug use, and daytime dysfunction. Each component (e.g., difficulty falling asleep within 30 minutes) is rated on a scale from 0 ("not during the past month") to 3 ("three or more times a week"). The global score is calculated by adding the scores of all seven components, ranging from 0 ("indicating no difficulty") to 21 ("indicating severe difficulty in all components"). Subjects who scored 5 or less had good sleep quality, whereas those who scored more than 5 had poor sleep quality (Neyazi et al. 2024).

Data analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS software (version 30). Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical data were analyzed using the χ^2 significance test. To compare two independent groups, the Student's *t*-test was used. Pearson correlation was employed to estimate the degree of correlation between two quantitative variables. A *p*-value of < 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all statistical tests.

Results

The study consisted of 175 women distributed into two main groups: the case group included 90 women with infertility, and the control group comprised 85 fertile women. The mean age \pm standard deviation of the study

population was 34.81 ± 5.90 years. It is evident that there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups regarding menstrual regularity and the Pittsburgh sleep quality index, while there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups regarding age and body mass index, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between the cases and controls regarding their ages and body mass index.

Variable	Cases = 90	Controls = 85	P-value
Age (years), mean \pm standard deviation	32.29 \pm 5.68	32.58 \pm 6.11	0.351
Body mass index (weight in kilograms/ (height in meter ²), mean \pm standard deviation)	25.56 \pm 2.90	25.24 \pm 2.94	0.249
Menstrual regularity, number (%)			
-Yes	35 (38.89%)	52 (61.1%)	0.002
-No	55 (61.11%)	33 (38.89%)	
Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI)			
- Good sleep	28 (31.1%)	50 (58.8%)	<0.001
- Poor sleep	62 (58.9%)	35 (41.2%)	

Table 2 shows a comparison between the cases and controls regarding their biochemical variables. The case group was found to have a statistically significant higher mean of insulin, HOMA-IR, and HOMA- β than the control group, but it had a statistically significant lower mean of QUICKI, insulin sensitivity, intelectin-1, and anti-Müllerian hormone. There was no statistically significant difference with regard to fasting blood sugar.

Table 2. Comparison between the cases and controls regarding their biochemical variables.

Variable	Cases = 90	Controls = 85	P-value
Fasting blood sugar, mean \pm standard deviation	91.03 \pm 9.47	90.39 \pm 9.70	0.329
Insulin level ($\mu\text{U/mL}$), mean \pm standard deviation	11.27 \pm 2.83	8.46 \pm 1.16	<0.001
Homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), mean \pm standard deviation	2.55 \pm 0.79	1.89 \pm 0.39	<0.001
Quantitative insulin sensitivity check index (QUICKI), mean \pm standard deviation	0.33 \pm 0.01	0.34 \pm 0.01	<0.001
Homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function % (HOMA- β), mean \pm standard deviation	162.90 \pm 76.54	124.13 \pm 41.59	<0.001
Insulin sensitivity, mean \pm standard deviation	0.43 \pm 0.17	0.54 \pm 0.01	<0.001
Intelectin-1 (ng/L), mean \pm standard deviation	202.31 \pm 57.93	392.31 \pm 37.27	<0.001
Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), mean \pm standard deviation	0.94 \pm 0.42	2.34 \pm 0.87	<0.001

Patients with insulin resistance were found to have statistically significantly lower intelectin-1 levels than those without insulin resistance. Furthermore, overweight patients were found to have statistically significantly lower intelectin-1 levels compared to normal-weight patients. Moreover, patients with irregular cycles had statistically significantly lower intelectin-1 levels. Lastly, patients with poor sleep had a statistically significant difference in intelectin-1 levels, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Comparison between patients with normal body mass index and overweight, regular and irregular menstrual cycles, and good and poor sleep regarding their mean intelectin-1 level.

Variable	Intelectin-1 levels, mean \pm standard deviation	P-value
Homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR)		
- Normal	347.78 \pm 99.73	<0.001
- Insulin resistance	258.29 \pm 95.78	
Body mass index		
- Normal	316.01 \pm 95.85	0.009
- Overweight	274.37 \pm 112.62	
Menstrual regularity		
- Regular	348.46 \pm 96.33	<0.001
- Irregular	251.10 \pm 98.63	
Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI)		
- Good sleep	334.29 \pm 73.41	<0.001
- Poor sleep	221.67 \pm 89.15	

Table 4 shows the correlation between serum intelectin-1 and different variables included in the study. The case group was found to have a significant, moderately negative correlation with body mass index, menstrual regularity, Pittsburgh sleep quality index, and fasting blood sugar. Furthermore, the case group showed a significant, moderately positive correlation with the homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function (%) and anti-Müllerian hormone. On the other hand, the control group showed a significant, mild negative correlation with body mass index, while it had a significant, moderately negative correlation with menstrual regularity, Pittsburgh sleep quality index, fasting blood sugar, insulin level, and homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance. Moreover, the control group was found to have a significant, mild positive correlation with patients' ages and homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function, while it had a significant, moderately positive correlation with quantitative insulin sensitivity check index, insulin sensitivity, and anti-Müllerian hormone.

Table 4. Correlation between serum intelectin-1 and different variables included in the study.

Variable	Cases = 90		Controls = 85	
	Correlation coefficient	P-value	Correlation coefficient	P-value
Patient age	-0.001	0.992	0.241	0.026
Body mass index	-0.580	<0.001	-0.313	0.003
Menstrual regularity	-0.404	<0.001	-0.614	<0.001
Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI)	-0.573	<0.001	-0.408	<0.001
Fasting blood sugar	-0.533	<0.001	-0.616	<0.001
Insulin level (μ u/mL)	0.062	0.561	-0.455	<0.001
Homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance (HOMA-IR)	-0.145	0.188	-0.628	<0.001
Quantitative insulin sensitivity check index (QUICKI)	0.093	0.383	0.610	<0.001
Homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function % (HOMA- β)	0.575	<0.001	0.363	<0.001
Insulin sensitivity	0.052	0.626	0.600	<0.001
Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH)	0.649	<0.001	0.481	<0.001

Table 5 and Figs 1–4 show the areas under the curve, cutoff values, and measurements of accuracy of different variables with regard to intelectin-1 level.

Figure 1. Receiver operating characteristic curve for intelectin-1 cutoff point for differentiation of insulin resistance.

Figure 2. Receiver operating characteristic curve for intelectin-1 cutoff point for differentiating normal from overweight and obesity.

At an intelectin-1 cutoff value of 355 ng/L, HOMA-IR was found to have a poor area under the curve (0.6691) with a test accuracy of 74.28%. Moreover, at an intelectin-1 cutoff value of 176.11 ng/L, body mass index was found to have a poor area under the curve (0.6247) with a test accuracy of 63.42%. At an intelectin-1 cutoff value of 397.54 ng/L, menstrual regularity was found to have an acceptable area under the curve (0.7627) with a test accuracy of 74.28%. Lastly, at an intelectin-1 cutoff value of 243.87 ng/L, the Pittsburgh sleep quality index was found to have an acceptable area under the curve (0.7803) and a test accuracy of 69.33%.

Table 5. Areas under the curve, cutoff values, and measurements of accuracy of different variables with regard to intelectin-1 level.

Variable	Area under the curve	Cutoff value	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive predicative value	Negative predicative value	Accuracy of the test
Homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance	0.6691	355	67.56%	79.20%	70.42%	76.92%	74.28%
Body mass index	0.6247	176.11	57.55%	86.11%	94.11%	34.44%	63.42%
Menstrual regularity	0.7627	397.54	93.75%	66.92%	51.72%	96.5%	74.28%
Pittsburgh sleep quality index (PSQI)	0.7803	243.87	63.8%	86.56%	88.46%	59.79%	69.33%

Figure 4. Receiver operating characteristic curve for intelectin-1 cutoff point for differentiating sleep quality.

Discussion

Understanding the association between intelectin-1, insulin resistance, and sleep in infertile women can help create specific therapies for these disorders. Women experiencing infertility may benefit from strategies targeted at modifying intelectin-1 levels, which could

regulate insulin resistance and improve sleep quality. The current study found that infertile patients, when compared with their fertile counterparts, showed a significantly higher incidence of menstrual cycle irregularity regardless of their body mass index, which is consistent with the findings of several studies (Aliu-Ayo et al. 2023; Patnaik et al. 2023). This suggests that weight is not a differentiating factor for infertility. However, it is worth noting that weight can also play a role in infertility, as overweight and obese women often experience menstrual irregularities due to anovulatory cycles (Zheng et al. 2024).

The current study found that infertile women generally report poorer sleep quality compared to their fertile counterparts. This difference is often indicated by higher PSQI scores in the infertile group, suggesting a potential link between infertility and sleep disturbances, as sleep disturbances can be both a consequence and a potential contributing factor to infertility. Comparable findings were obtained from a study conducted in Istanbul (Özçelik et al. 2023).

The study found that infertile women often have significantly higher levels of fasting insulin, HOMA-IR (homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance), and HOMA- β (homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function) compared to fertile women. These findings suggest that insulin resistance and impaired pancreatic β -cell function may play a role in female infertility by decreasing the body's ability to respond to insulin and affecting various aspects of female reproductive health, including ovulation, egg quality, and embryo implantation. This agrees with other studies (Dawood et al. 2024; Bahreiny et al. 2025).

On the other hand, the study found that infertile women often exhibit lower levels of QUICKI (quantitative insulin sensitivity check index), insulin sensitivity, intelectin-1, and anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) compared to fertile women. The interconnected effect of lower insulin sensitivity, decreased intelectin-1, and potentially altered AMH levels contributes to the reproductive challenges faced by infertile women, particularly those with PCOS. This is consistent with a study on intelectin-1 and endocrinological parameters in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (Al-Fartosy et al. 2020).

The study compared intelectin-1 levels between different groups regarding HOMA-IR and overweight. Intelectin-1 was found to be significantly lower in patients with high HOMA-IR (more than 2) and in overweight ladies, indicating insulin resistance, compared

to those with normal HOMA-IR and healthy weight. This finding highlights a potential role of intelectin-1 in the development of metabolic disorders associated with insulin resistance and obesity, such as type 2 diabetes. Comparable findings were obtained from a study on the relationship between intelectin-1, glycaemic control, and metabolic parameters (Elsaid et al. 2018). Similarly, intelectin-1 was found in this study to be significantly lower among ladies with menstrual irregularity compared to those with regular cycles, which is consistent with an assessment study of different serum proteins, including intelectin-1, among ladies with polycystic ovary syndrome (Guvenc et al. 2018). Lastly, the study found that patients with poor sleep had significantly lower levels of intelectin-1 than those with good sleep, which is similar to another study's findings (Ibáñez-Del Valle et al. 2024).

Intelectin-1 (ITLN-1) was found in this study to have a significant, moderately negative correlation with BMI in the case group and a significant, mild negative correlation with BMI in the control group. This suggests that higher ITLN-1 levels are associated with lower BMI in both groups, but the relationship is stronger in the case group. Given obesity's impact on the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis and the hormonal balance of fertility, ITLN-1 may be involved in these processes. This is consistent with a study conducted in Germany (Czechowski et al. 2024). Likewise, intelectin-1 was found in this study to have a significant, moderately negative correlation in both case and control groups with menstrual regularity, suggesting that intelectin-1 plays a role in regulating menstrual cycles. However, there is no human study that directly assesses the correlation between intelectin-1 and menstrual regularity. Nevertheless, in a published study conducted in Basra, Iraq, intelectin-1 among ladies with polycystic ovary syndrome was significantly lower among PCOS patients than controls, indicating a negative correlation with menstrual regularity (Al-Fartosy et al. 2020).

Regarding the correlation between intelectin-1 and sleep quality, the study found that both cases and controls had a significant, moderately negative correlation between intelectin-1 and sleep quality. This suggests that intelectin-1 may play a role in sleep regulation and that higher levels of this protein are associated with poorer sleep in both infertile and fertile women. Another study also found a significant negative correlation between intelectin-1 and sleep quality (Ibáñez-Del Valle et al. 2024). Similarly, intelectin-1 was found in this study to have a significant, moderately positive correlation with HOMA- β in the case group and, to a lesser extent, in the control group. This indicates that intelectin-1 might be more crucial for β -cell function in individuals with infertility and that β -cell function improves as intelectin-1 levels increase. In contrast, another study suggested a negative correlation between intelectin-1 and β -cell function (Mahde et al. 2009).

However, further research is needed to explore the mechanisms underlying this correlation and to determine whether intelectin-1 could be a potential therapeutic target for metabolic disorders and infertility.

In the same way, intelectin-1 was found in this study to have a significant, moderately positive correlation with anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) in both case and control groups, which suggests that the more intelectin-1 a woman has, the more likely she is to have a good supply of eggs (as indicated by AMH levels), regardless of whether she is currently experiencing infertility. However, further studies are needed to understand the precise mechanisms and clinical significance of this relationship; specifically, it would be beneficial to investigate whether manipulating ITLN-1 levels could influence AMH and, consequently, fertility outcomes. Consistent findings were obtained from a study conducted in Baghdad (Mohammed and Haddad 2024). Only the control group showed a significant, mild negative correlation with patient age and a moderately negative correlation with insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), as well as a significant, moderately positive correlation with QUICKI. This suggests that intelectin-1 levels need to be maintained within a specific, healthy range for optimal reproductive health. Both abnormally high and low levels of ITLN-1 have been associated with fertility issues, as increased levels of ITLN-1 are linked to inflammatory problems, while low ITLN-1 levels have also been associated with fertility problems, potentially due to its role in regulating insulin sensitivity and metabolic processes. Moreover, interventions to regulate ITLN-1 levels might be beneficial for some individuals struggling with infertility, but careful monitoring and individualized approaches are necessary (Al-Fartosy et al. 2020).

At specific intelectin-1 cutoff values, various variables showed varying degrees of correlation with intelectin-1 levels. Specifically, HOMA-IR and body mass index had poor areas under the curve at certain cutoff levels, while menstrual regularity and the Pittsburgh sleep quality index showed acceptable areas under the curve at other specific cutoff levels for intelectin-1. These findings suggest that using a specific cutoff value for intelectin-1 as an indicator of insulin resistance and overweight or obesity may not be highly reliable. However, intelectin-1 can be considered an acceptable indicator for menstrual irregularity and sleep quality. Further studies are needed to confirm these findings, as no published research has yet reported such cutoff points.

Conclusion

Intelectin is an accepted biomarker for the assessment of menstrual irregularity and sleep quality, as it showed acceptable accuracy in predicting these conditions. Intelectin-1 has a significant negative correlation with

body mass index, menstrual regularity, the Pittsburgh sleep quality index, and fasting blood sugar regulation, while it has a significant positive correlation with the homeostatic model assessment for β -cell function and anti-Müllerian hormone. More studies are needed to confirm the exact accuracy of intelectin-1 and its correlation with insulin resistance and sleep quality to better assess its role in improving treatment options for women with infertility.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

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The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Use of AI

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Author contributions

Concept: M.H.M., J.A.M. Design the research study: J.A.M., M.H.M. Data Collection and Analysis: M.H.M., J.A.M Interpretation: M.H.M., J.A.M., S.A.A.: Literature Search: J.A.M., M.H.M., S.A.A.: Writing: J.A.M., M.H.M., S.H.I. All authors contributed to the revision and approval of the final manuscript.

Author ORCIDs

Jehan A. Mohammad <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6831-7619>
Marwah H. Mohammed <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3597-0851>
Safaa A. Al-Ameen <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2953-7242>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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